

OrganKits project

OrganKits partners have been working in the project and have several updates to share! The project's key milestones are presented in this 1st newsletter. Want to find more? Contact us or visit our website

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Meet OrganKits project

OrganKits - a new material for STEAM education based on plastination aims to create a new educational material (OrganKits) for STEAM...

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OrganKits Kick-off Meeting

OrganKits partners met in Murcia on the 27th and 28th of February 2023, for the project's kick-off meeting, with all the partners attending.

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The first OrganKits are being developed

OrganKits partners have already started working on the first products of the project. School partners are already designing the Educational Guides...

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